

Transfer of Learning Mediated by Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract

In the age of artificial intelligence (AI), we must consider not only the loss of cognitive friction and cognitive laziness associated with its use, but also the role of AI in transfer learning. In fact, without it, the importance of transfer is not always taken into account, nor are real ways sought to assess it. Likewise, it is important to understand the assistant's dilemma: the balance between support and autonomy.

A crucial contribution of AI to the personalization of learning in general, and specifically to transfer, is on the horizon. This paper aims to provide an analysis of how we might measure transfer learning. The focus is on the indicators for specialists and teachers according to Barnett and Ceci, with the goal of creating a taxonomy useful for understanding the teaching-learning process.

1. Conceptualization and Characterization of Transfer Learning

Transfer learning is a recurring concept in education, referring to the ability to apply knowledge, skills, or strategies acquired in one context to new or different situations. From a Vygotskian perspective, transfer is understood as a process mediated by cultural and social tools, where learning is not simply an accumulation of information but an active construction that allows for the application of what has been learned in various contexts, as it involves metacognitive mechanisms (Leyes, 2013).

It is important to consider some of its aspects, such as the types of transfer, its relationship to situated cognition, conceptual change, the importance of generic

and episodic knowledge, the role of metacognitive processes, and cross-contextual.

Perkins and Salomon (1999) delve into the mechanisms of transfer, distinguishing between reflective transfer (low-level or low-route) and conscious transfer (high-level or high-route). Reflexive transfer occurs when stimulus conditions are like those in the learning context, are automated, and result from repeated practice, whereas conscious transfer involves deliberate abstraction and a search for connections between contexts. This distinction is crucial for understanding how students can apply knowledge in similar contexts (near transfer) or in significantly different contexts (far transfer). This model suggests that transfer is not automatic but requires specific conditions to be promoted, such as teaching in multiple contexts and the use of metacognitive strategies.

Returning to the text, Leyes poses a paradox between situated cognition and transfer, asking whether it is possible to transfer knowledge when each situation requires specific knowledge that may not be suitable for other similar yet different situations. According to the author, the situated nature of knowledge not only does not prevent transfer but requires it. Furthermore, he analyzes whether conceptual change facilitates the transfer of knowledge or whether it is transfer that drives conceptual change, advocating the latter position in conjunction with the former. He notes that we must highlight the importance of generic and episodic knowledge --- that is, how we interpret situations based on generic conceptual structures and how interaction with each situation constructs learning (episodic knowledge) that modifies the generic structures. Finally, he acknowledges the role of metacognitive processes and cross-disciplinary emphasizes that one learns to transfer knowledge through metacognitive processes that make explicit the differences between domains and contexts, promoting the versatile application of what has been learned across multiple contexts rather than decontextualizing the content.

Transfer learning is a complex process that depends on the student's ability to abstract generalizable principles, the quality of the feedback received, and the adaptation of tutoring systems to individual needs. But how might these concepts be applied to the context of artificial intelligence-mediated learning?

2. The Relationship Between Transfer and Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence (AI) is expected to have significant potential to facilitate the transfer of learning, but its effectiveness would depend on how educational systems are designed and implemented. Returning to the Vygotskian perspective, AI can act as that mediating tool that expands human cognitive capacities, allowing students to tackle more complex tasks and transfer knowledge to new contexts through scaffolding in education and learning that is programmed and carefully evaluated by the teacher (Leyes, 2013).

Perkins, Bloerson, and Salomon, G. (1992) distinguish between the "WITH" effects of technology (improved performance during interaction) and the "OF" effects of technology (transferable cognitive residue after interaction). AI can improve performance while it is being used, but the key challenge is ensuring that this interaction also leads to an "OF" effect --- that is, that students develop skills and strategies they can transfer to other situations, even when they do not have access to AI.

2.1 Personalization and Transfer

AI can personalize learning by adapting the order of the material to optimize transfer, as noted by Roll and Wylie (2016). Adaptive learning systems can design active learning experiences that foster near- and far-transfer. However, too much personalization could act as a "crutch," hindering transfer to non-personalized situations. To review the effectiveness of tutoring systems, Lehn (2011) analyzes them in terms of promoting transfer. Step-based Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS) have proven to be nearly as effective as human tutoring, with an average effectiveness of $d = 0.76$. However, response-based systems tend to have lower effectiveness ($d = 0.31$). There is a hypothesis of an "interaction plateau" where effectiveness increases from response-based tutoring to step-based tutoring but further decreases in the granularity of the user interface (sub-step-based tutoring, human tutoring) do not increase effectiveness. In summary, step-based ITSs offer an effective alternative that is potentially more comparable to human tutoring. According to the author, it is relevant to consider other concepts, such as granularity, feedback, and scaffolding.

The granularity of interaction refers to the amount of reasoning required of participants during the various opportunities to interact with the system. The larger the granularity of the user interface, the more reasoning is required per interaction.

For example, an answer-based tutoring system requires the student to perform all the reasoning necessary to solve the problem between interactions, whereas an Intelligent Tutoring System (ITS) provides many opportunities to interact with the tutor while solving the problem. The interaction granularity hypothesis posits that the effectiveness of tutoring systems increases as the granularity of the system's interaction decreases.

In human tutoring, feedback helps students detect and adapt their knowledge because it facilitates self-correction. If a student makes hundreds of mental inferences while solving a problem, and an answer-based tutoring system says the answer is incorrect, then any one of those hundreds of inferences could be wrong. This makes it difficult for students to identify the incorrect inference and improve their knowledge. In contrast, if a human tutor is eliciting the student's reasoning as they work and indicates that the student's most recent statement is incorrect, then the student knows that one of the most recent inferences is incorrect. Self-correction is much easier when feedback refers to a few inferences (human tutoring) than when it refers to many inferences (response-based tutoring).

Scaffolding by the teacher involves nudging the student a little further along a line of reasoning through collaborative execution (e.g., prompting) and coordination (e.g., connecting to reality, knowledge sharing). When a human tutor tells the student, "That sounds good to me. Keep going," the tutor is indicating mutual understanding (coordination), accepting the student's reasoning (collaborative execution), and indicating who should continue the execution (collaborative execution). A step-based tutoring system also provides scaffolding to a student, but in a different way.

Building on what Lehn (2011) has been arguing so far, the interplay between interaction granularity, feedback, and scaffolding with transfer in AI-mediated learning is fundamental to designing personalized and effective educational systems.

- Granularity of Interaction and Transfer: The granularity of interaction directly affects the student's ability to apply knowledge in new contexts. AI systems with lower granularity (such as systems based on steps or sub-steps) allow for more frequent and specific interaction, facilitating the identification and correction of errors in the student's reasoning. This promotes deeper understanding and,

consequently, greater knowledge transfer. If the AI can interact with the student at every small step of the reasoning process, the student has more opportunities to internalize concepts and apply them in varied situations.

- Feedback and Transfer: Effective feedback is crucial for transfer. Answer-based tutoring systems, which provide feedback only at the end of a problem, make it difficult to identify specific errors, thereby reducing the capacity for transfer. In contrast, AI systems that provide immediate and specific feedback at every step of the problem-solving process (such as step - based ITS) help students detect and correct their reasoning errors, which facilitates the generalization of knowledge to new contexts.

- Scaffolding and Transfer: Scaffolding is a technique that provides temporary support to students so they can solve problems that are beyond their current level of competence. In AI systems, scaffolding can take the form of "hints," guided questions, or solved examples. By providing the right support at the right time, scaffolding helps students develop problem-solving skills and build a deeper understanding of concepts, which facilitates the transfer of knowledge to new situations.

For example, an AI system might start by providing a high level of scaffolding at the beginning, guiding the student through each step of the problem-solving process. As the student becomes more competent, the system could gradually reduce this support, allowing the student to take on more responsibility for solving the problem.

To conclude the discussion of Lehn's concepts in this section, the concept of the "interaction plateau" suggests that while increasing the granularity of interaction is beneficial up to a certain point, beyond a certain level (such as moving from step-by-step guidance to human tutoring), the additional benefits are minimal. This has important implications for the design of AI systems, as it suggests that it is not necessary to fully replicate human interaction to achieve effective learning. Instead, AI designers should focus on optimizing the granularity of interaction, feedback, and scaffolding to maximize knowledge transfer.

All the factors mentioned allow students to develop a deeper understanding of concepts and apply knowledge in a variety of contexts, preparing them for the challenges of the future. But how effective is assistance from a human guide versus an AI guide?

3. The Assistance Dilemma

The balance between support and autonomy is critical. AI systems that prioritize immediate feedback could hinder long-term transfer by reducing the need for creative adaptation. Examples such as the use of algorithms in gambling versus financial analysis illustrate the risks of excessive dependence. In 2011, Walkington and Maull addressed the dilemma of when and how much assistance to provide to facilitate learning without creating dependency. AI must balance assistance with the need for students to face desirable challenges, which improves skill transfer and metacognitive reflection by providing proactive cues.

According to Koedinger and Alevan (2007), there are general conditions under which the amount of feedback may be appropriate depending on various situations. Here are six situations with their respective conditions and analyses:

- Immediate vs. Delayed Feedback:

- Scenario: Provide feedback (yes/no) immediately after the student's response or delay it.

- Conditions: Immediate feedback appears to be more effective at minimizing "floundering" (difficulty making progress) and keeping students on track. However, delayed feedback could be beneficial in specific situations where the goal is to encourage self-assessment and error detection.

- Parameters: Koedinger and Alevan compare the 1995 study by Corbett and Anderson, in which these authors found that immediate feedback leads to faster learning, with the 2005 study by Mathan and Koedinger, who explored a "smart beginner" approach in which students are allowed to make initial errors and then correct them, suggesting that a certain degree of delayed or error-tolerant feedback might be beneficial.

- Feedback Content (Explanatory vs. Yes/No):

- Scenario: Providing feedback that includes detailed explanations of why an answer is correct or incorrect, rather than simply indicating whether it is correct or not.

- Conditions: Explanatory feedback is most useful when it helps reduce "floundering" and makes the learning process more explicit. It is particularly valuable when it provides information about the goals the student should pursue.

- Parameters: Another cited study by Koedinger and Alevan, from McKendree in 1990, demonstrated that feedback with information about goals improves performance and reduces the error rate.

- Hints (on-demand vs. proactive):

- Scenario: Offering hints only when the student requests them (on-demand) or providing them proactively after a certain number of errors.

- Conditions: Cognitive Tutors generally offer hints on demand to balance the provision and retention of information. However, evidence suggests that students are not always good at seeking help at the right time. Therefore, it might be beneficial to provide hints proactively, especially after the student has made several errors.

- Parameters: Data from Cognitive Tutors indicate that students often use "bottom-out" hints (which give the answer directly) without reading the preceding ones that explain the reasoning. This suggests that proactive hints might be more effective if presented gradually, starting with general explanations and then becoming more specific.

- Worked Examples vs. Problem Solving:

- Scenario: Alternating between solved examples (where the solution is shown step-by-step) and problem-solving (where the student must find the solution on their own).

- Conditions: Solved examples are more useful for beginners, as they reduce cognitive load and provide a model to follow. However, as students gain more experience, problem-solving becomes more effective for consolidating knowledge.

- Parameters: The 2007 study by Schwonke cited by Koedinger and Aleven found that a gradual transition from solved examples to problem-solving ("faded examples") is more effective than using only solved examples or only problem-solving.

- Support for Self-Explanation:

- Scenario: Encouraging students to explain the reasoning behind each step in a solved example or in problem-solving.

- Conditions: Self-explanation can significantly improve learning, especially when combined with feedback on the correctness of the explanations. However, students may not be motivated to self-explain without the presence of an experimenter or without feedback.

- Mastery vs. Metacognitive learning:

- Scenario: Cognitive tutors assess students' mastery of knowledge components and select problems based on individual needs. Mastery-based tutors focus on subject-specific knowledge, while metacognitive tutors focus on teaching students how to learn and solve problems effectively.

- Conditions: Metacognitive learning is most effective for students who lack the skills to regulate their own learning. Metacognitive support may include feedback on students' help-seeking behavior and strategies.

An optimal balance between the provision and retention of information depends on the specific learning context, student characteristics, and instructional objectives. Specific parameters are needed to guide instructional design decisions.

4. The Need for a Taxonomy of Far Transfer

The controversy surrounding transfer of learning, and in particular far transfer, centers on the debate over whether skills and knowledge acquired in one context can be successfully applied to significantly different contexts. There is disagreement regarding the nature, scope, and underlying mechanisms of transfer. Some researchers, such as Detterman, Halpern, Brown, Fong, Herrstein, Ceci, and Ruiz, cited by Barnett and Ceci (2002), argue that far transfer is rare or nonexistent or varies greatly. Detterman (1993) argued that current educational philosophy lacks empirical support, since meaningful transfer is very rare and education focuses primarily on the memorization of information. Others assert that far transfer is possible under certain conditions. Halpern (1998) suggests that critical thinking can be learned in ways that promote transfer to novel contexts. Brown (1989) demonstrated that children can transfer causal principles to new contexts if they understand events at a deep causal level.

The controversy is intensified by the lack of a clear and agreed-upon definition of what constitutes "transfer" and "a new context." The lack of a common structure in transfer studies makes it difficult to conduct a definitive meta-analysis.

Barnett and Ceci (2002) propose a taxonomy for transfer that considers multiple contextual and content dimensions. These dimensions include:

- Nature of the skill to be transferred (specific vs. general)
- Change in measured performance (speed, accuracy, quality)
- Memory demands of the transfer task (recall, recognition, execution)
- Contextual distance between training and transfer in terms of:
 - Knowledge domain: Refers to the knowledge base to which the skill is applied. Example: Transferring skills learned in physics class to chemistry class is considered a closer transfer than transferring them to English class, since physics and chemistry share more elements in common.
 - Physical context: This includes both macro (school, laboratory, home) and micro (same room, same experimenter) aspects of the environment where learning and transfer occur. Example: Fong et al. (1991) assessed the transfer of statistical

knowledge learned in a college course to students' homes by simulating a telephone survey. This is an example of transfer to a different physical context.

- Temporal context: Refers to the time elapsed between the training phase and the assessment phase. Example: Most studies assess transfer shortly after training. However, to justify investment in education, one would ideally expect the transfer to last for several years.

- Functional context: This is the function for which the skill is intended and the mindset it evokes in the individual. Example: A skill learned as an academic activity may not transfer equally well to a "real-world" situation outside of academia. The study by Ceci and Ruiz (1993) on the transfer of horse racing betting skills to stock market analysis illustrates this point.

- Social context: This refers to whether the task is learned and performed alone or in collaboration with others. Example: A skill acquired in a group setting may not apply equally well when working alone, or vice versa.

- Modality: This refers to the format of the task, whether visual or auditory, written or verbal, linguistic or practical. Example: Transfer may differ if the assessment is in multiple-choice format rather than an essay. Herrnstein et al. (1986) found that the benefits of a thinking skills program varied depending on the test format.

The taxonomy aims to provide a structure for analyzing and comparing transfer studies, identifying the conditions under which far transfer is most likely. They argue that many successful transfer studies only demonstrate near transfer.

Some examples of studies suggesting the possibility of far transfer include students in a statistics course who applied their knowledge to everyday questions about sports at home; elementary school children who transferred the "control of variables" strategy to different domains several months after training; and evidence of transfer from science class to English exams taken 2 years after an intervention to train metacognitive skills.

However, even these studies have limitations, according to Barnett and Ceci, such as a lack of spontaneity in transfer or the difficulty in determining which aspects of the context are most important.

The taxonomy proposed by the authors offers a framework for analyzing these factors and guiding future research in this field. It is time to contextualize it within AI. But this inevitably requires the teacher's participation.

Conclusions

This study explored the concepts developed by various authors regarding AI-mediated learning transfer, highlighting its potential as a cognitive mediation tool in line with the Vygotskian perspective. Among the key contributions for further study of AI-mediated Transfer learning are:

a) The distinction between reflective and conscious transfer (Perkins & Salomon, 1999), where AI can optimize the latter through scaffolding and granular feedback. The paradox (Leyes, 2013) between situated cognition and transfer, analyzes the value of conceptual change, knowledge (both generic and episodic), the role of metacognitive processes, and cross-disciplinary for a versatile and comprehensive understanding of what we mean by transfer learning.

b) The role of personalization in Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS), which, although effective, according to Lehn (2011), requires balance to avoid dependency and must account for the interaction plateau to measure other types of evidence in student performance.

c) The dilemma of assistance, regarding the appropriateness of the timing and amount of assistance to be provided to facilitate learning, according to Walkington and Maull (2011).

d) The need to implement a taxonomy, as proposed by Barnett and Ceci (2002), to establish a common framework for evaluating far transfer, applicable to AI design in diverse educational contexts.

The limitations of this study may include:

- A certain bias in the analyzed literature: most of the reviewed studies (e.g., Lehn, 2011; Koedinger & Alevan, 2007) focus on specific domains (mathematics, science), which limit generalization to areas such as the arts or the humanities.
- Ambiguous definitions: the lack of consensus on terms such as "far transfer" (Barnett & Ceci, 2002) makes it difficult to compare studies.
- Artificial contexts as settings for analysis: many ITS experiments are conducted in controlled environments, without considering real-world classroom variables (e.g., cultural diversity, limited resources).
- Lack of temporal perspective: the long-term impact of AI on transfer is not addressed (e.g., how it affects knowledge retention years later).

Given the above, suggestions for further exploration of the topic could include either enabling future researchers to find additional literature in other languages (studies were analyzed in English and Spanish) or, based on these limitations, having other studies bridge the gap between what is real and what is transferable to many more educational contexts. Among these, the following are suggested as new lines of research:

- 1) AI and metacognition: studying how AI systems can foster metacognitive processes (e.g., self-regulation) to facilitate far transfer.
- 2) Ethics and algorithmic biases: investigating the impact of biases in AI algorithms on equity in education, especially among populations with disabilities or giftedness.
- 3) Human-AI interaction: exploring the optimal level of granularity in tutoring (step-based vs. sub-step-based) and its relationship to student autonomy.
- 4) Development of dynamic taxonomies: develop transfer assessment frameworks adaptable to different domains (STEM, humanities) and contexts (physical, virtual).
- 5) Integration of paradigms: AI challenges classical learning theories (behaviorism, constructivism) by introducing non-human mediation. How can this be reconciled with existing pedagogical models?

Transfer learning is a challenging process that requires a deep understanding of the cognitive and contextual mechanisms that facilitate it. AI has the potential to improve transfer, especially when designed to foster conscious abstraction, metacognitive reflection, and the application of knowledge across multiple

contexts. However, its effectiveness depends on how the challenges associated with its implementation are addressed, ranging from teacher training to ethical concerns. Furthermore, we must account for the specific needs of learners with varying degrees of disability and giftedness. Understanding self-paced learning is a challenge that sometimes seems to clash with the current vision of mass education. And paradoxically, even under these conditions, it does not seem easy to plan and evaluate diverse assessment models that measure transfer learning.

Could this be an opportunity for us, in teaching and learning with AI, to truly reevaluate the effectiveness of learning through transfer? Is transfer always the same as assessment? New measurement models are certainly needed, so an appropriate taxonomy would bring us closer to the precision required to learn from evidence --- evidence examined not only by researchers but by the real actors in the classroom: teachers and students.

BIBLIOGRAPHICAL REFERENCES

Barnett, S. M. & Ceci, S. J. (2002). When and where do we apply what we learn? A taxonomy for far transfer. *Psychological Bulletin*, 128(4), 612–637.

Koedinger, K.R., & Alevan, V. (2007). Exploring the Assistance Dilemma in Experiments with Cognitive Tutors. *Educational Psychologist*, 19, 239–264.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-007-9049-0>

Lehn, K. (2011). The relative effectiveness of human tutoring, intelligent tutoring systems, and other tutoring systems. *Educational Psychologist*, 46(4), 197–221.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2011.611369>

Lema Balla, J. C., Allauca Peñafiel, D. R., García López, J. L., Moya Romero, F. J., & Lema Balla, J. R. (2024). Impact of Artificial Intelligence on the Transfer of Scientific Knowledge: Resilience and Challenges for University Faculty. *Arandu UTIC*, 11(2), 3008–3024. <https://doi.org/10.69639/arandu.v11i2.457>

Leyes, R. (2013). The Transfer of Learning from the Vygotskian Perspective of Situated Cognition. Paper prepared for the "Cognitive Change and Learning" seminar at the Latin American Faculty of Social Sciences (FLACSO).

Perkins, D., & Salomon, G. (1999). Transfer of Learning. *International Encyclopedia of Education* (2nd ed.).

Perkins, D., Bloerson, T., & Salomon, G. (1992). Co-creating knowledge: Expanding human intelligence with intelligent technologies. *CL & E: Communication, Language, and Education*, No. 13, pp. 6–22.

Roll, I., & Wylie, R. (2016). Evolution and Revolution in Artificial Intelligence in Education. *IJAIE*, Vol. 26, No. 2.

Selwyn, N. (2019). *Should robots replace teachers?* Polity Press. Cambridge.
<https://www.wiley.com/en-se/Should+Robots+Replace+Teachers%3F%3A+AI+and+the+Future+of+Education-p-9781509528967tableofcontents-section>

Walkington, C., & Maull, K. (2011). Exploring the assistance dilemma: The case of context personalization. In *Proceedings of the 33rd Annual Conference of the Cognitive Science Society*.